

EFFECTIVENESS OF USING DIDACTIC GAMES IN PRIMARY CLASS LESSONS

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Abstract. *This article discusses the relevance of using didactic games in primary school classes, based on the theory and opinions about the use of didactic games in the lesson processes organized for any subject in the primary school.*

Keywords: *didactic game, primary class lessons, preschool education, modern technologies, task of didactic games.*

As a result of the deepening of the process of globalization in the world, the demand for competitive, comprehensively mature, legally cultured personnel is increasing. There is no doubt that the successful implementation of fundamental reforms in the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan depends on the qualifications of the personnel currently working in the sectors considered important for the development of our country, their legal consciousness, knowledge and outlook. The new reforms implemented in the field of preschool education and primary education in our country today have led to radical changes in these areas. The introduction of modern new technologies into the practice of preschool and primary education is an important step in the effective organization of the activities of the fields. However, the need to pay attention to the factors that play an important role in this process in the quality education of children receiving education in preschool and primary education organizations emerges with urgency.

During the past period, we have organized an effective system of pre-school and primary education aimed at bringing the growing generation in our country to a healthy and comprehensively mature adult, introducing effective forms and methods of education and upbringing into the educational process. wide-scale work has been carried out. The President of our Republic, Sh. Mirziyoyev, is paying special attention to the development of the preschool and elementary education system, which are the first and most important links of the education of the young generation. In particular, this issue was discussed in detail at the meetings held on August 16 and October 19, 2017. On September 30, 2017, the Honorable President issued the Decree "On measures to radically improve the management of the preschool education system" and the Decree "On the organization of the Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan" the decision was made. During the meetings of the head of state during his visits to the regions, many tasks were defined in this regard. "If we do not properly form their consciousness and thinking from infancy, attracting qualified and competent pedagogues who can approach each child individually to the process of raising children, we will not be able to achieve a high level of education, knowledge and spirituality in the future. it will be difficult to raise a mature generation that we have" - said Sh.M. Mirziyoyev. For this purpose, first of all, special attention was paid to increasing the coverage of preschool education organizations for children under 7 years of age, as well as providing them with quality education and upbringing.

In particular, based on these tasks, the number of state and non-state pre-school education organizations (private, public-private partnership, family) has been dramatically increased, and the coverage of children is gradually increasing in a planned manner. Preschool education in our

republic is based on the State Curriculum of the preschool education organization "Ilk Kadam" adopted by the Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2018 and the state requirements for the development of primary and preschool children of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The development of game competence of children of educational institutions was accepted as a new field of education. For this reason, despite the fact that scientists of our republic have carried out significant scientific research on this issue, the pedagogical possibilities of developing the game competence of preschool children have not been fully explored. For this reason, today, the relevance of using didactic games in primary school mother tongue and reading literacy classes is evident.

Didactic games, in terms of their form, are mainly creative games played in the training processes of preschool educational organizations, which the teacher himself explains by telling a story and makes the students learn. also differs from one-sided games that are reinforced by one-on-one inquiry. Didactic games serve the purpose of teaching and are conducted at an interesting, fun, and comprehensible level. Children train with all their heart to win, they get used to completing every given task, as a result, their interest in doing didactic tasks increases. Didactic games help to better understand the purpose of each lesson, the goals and tasks of each exercise. Didactic games include visuality of education, teacher's speech and children's actions, as a result of which unity is born in perception (sight, hearing, skin sensation signs). This encourages children to think about what the teacher said and express what was said, that is, to fulfill the rules of the didactic game themselves. The structure of didactic games in this way makes it possible to analyze the activity of students. That's why all children act with great interest during the game.

There can be no real mental development without play. The game is a spark that arouses enthusiasm and interest in learning in students. The game is a method used by adults, that is, teachers, educators, parents, to form certain qualities in elementary school students. With the help of the game, the learning process of students becomes easier, they learn to deal with various objects, and also the culture of behavior is formed in them. The child's personality is formed by means of the game, in which the mental characteristics related to the organization of educational and work activities and entering into relations with people are formed in the future. Through play, children learn about existence and try to change the world. Thus, the game lays the foundation for the formation of human activity.

In the game, a person shows the ability to reflect existence. The most important importance of the game is that the child's need to influence the world first appears and is formed in it. By school years, game forms develop more broadly. The student's game activity is of interest to scientists of many fields, that is, philosophers, sociologists, biologists, art historians, ethnographers, especially pedagogues and psychologists.

In psychology, play is considered to be of crucial importance in the development of the child's psyche. All aspects of a child's personality are formed in unity and interaction only in the game. The game creates an important basis for the transition to a higher stage of development in the child's psyche. A didactic game is an active activity in the field of creating an imitative model of the studied events and phenomena. An important difference of the game from other types of activity is that its subject is human activity. The main type of activity in the didactic game is cooperative learning activity.

Today, under the leadership of our president, great attention is being paid to the use of computer technologies in our republic, so it is necessary for a person to show himself as a user of

computer technologies in his work. Because the whole life of a person consists of storing information and receiving it. However, no matter how perfect the human brain is, it cannot store all the huge amounts of information in its memory and completely deliver it to the next generation. Therefore, it is necessary to use information technologies. In fact, information technologies are the basis for ensuring the successful development of science and technology, and the development of innovation and intellectual activity of students. In this regard, the use of information technologies in the process of education and upbringing has led to the need to teach information technologies first of all in order to increase the effectiveness of education. Therefore, it is necessary to develop the skills of working with a computer in elementary school students. In order to solve this problem, the order of the Ministry of Public Education dated June 9, 2011 No. 123 "On approval of the curriculum for general education schools for the 2011-2012 school year" organization of computer science classes in 2-4 grades according to the hours at the school's disposal. Completing the tasks specified in the order, that is, developing a system for using computers and information technologies in primary education, means increasing the level of computer literacy of students. Because this subject, which is taught in primary education, can teach ways to arm yourself with information technologies. Nowadays, with the help of computer technology, it is possible to calculate, write, read, learn, speak, draw, make models, receive information, process, play. In this regard, it is also used in the teaching of science in primary classes, using multimedia tools to demonstrate natural phenomena, to control and master the knowledge, skills and abilities of students. It is also possible to demonstrate this in the form of a lesson to children as a didactic game. This not only helps children learn about information technologies, but also increases the importance of didactic games.

The traditions of wide use of didactic games in the education and upbringing of children, which have been formed in folk pedagogy, have been developed in the practical experiences of teachers and the work of scientists. Czech pedagogue Ya.A. Comenius emphasized that the game is the main form of the child's activity and said that the game corresponds to the child's nature and interests. The scientist emphasizes that the game develops the mental abilities of the child in every way, expands his imagination about the environment, and develops his speech. It also brings them closer to their peers for peer-to-peer play. Based on this idea, it is no exaggeration to say that by using didactic games in children's education, it is possible to form a well-rounded person and to achieve great opportunities in elucidating didactic goals.

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